

Impact of Foundational Literacy and Numeracy Programme in Academic Achievement in Govt. Primary Schools of Varanasi

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Abstract:

Government of India, Ministry of Education has noticed the broad lacking in Foundational Literacy and Numeracy skills among the students with and without disabilities enrolled in Govt. primary schools in grade-1, grade-2 and grade-3. NIPUN Bharat Mission is one the dream project of Government of India, Ministry of Education by which the most challenging skills particular Literacy and Numeracy is being targeted to enhanced among the targeted group. The abstract presents a comprehensive overview of the status of literacy and numeracy in the context of the global education landscape, with a focus on the situation in India, particularly in the state of Uttar Pradesh. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education is highlighted, showcasing the decline in language and math skills among students due to prolonged school closures. The NIPUN Bharat Mission is discussed as responses to these challenges. The methodology used for a study conducted in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, aimed to measure foundational literacy and numeracy skills among students with and without disabilities from grades 1 to 3. The study's population, sample size, treatment strategies, data collection methods and analysis techniques are in detailed. Results from the study indicate significant improvements in both language and math proficiency among students after the implementation of the Foundational Literacy and Numeracy programme of 22 weeks. The correlation between student attendance and literacy-numeracy skills is also explored, emphasizing the importance of attendance in academic performance.

Key words: *FLN, NIPUN, Literacy, Numeracy, Prerna etc.*

Introduction:

The NIPUN Bharat mission is one the dream project of Government of India (GoI) by which the most challenging skills particular Literacy and Numeracy is being enhanced among students with and without disabilities. The GoI has been taking numerous initiatives through different flagship schemes and programmes for the improvement of education in India in terms of enrollment, quality education, scholarships, qualitative research and teacher's training & opening more new pioneer institutions. According to census 2011 more than 10% children are affected with various disabilities and they are deprived from basic education & mainstreaming and also unproductive in National development.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 places a strong emphasis on measures that are in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 2030. The

policy recognizes that without achieving this basic level of learning (reading, writing, and arithmetic) the other aspects of the policy might not effectively serve a significant portion of students.

To realize this vision, the GoI introduced the National Mission on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy on July 5th, 2021. This initiative is called the 'National Initiative for Proficiency in Reading with Understanding and Numeracy' (NIPUN Bharat Mission). The Department of School Education and Literacy (DoSE&L) within the Ministry of Education (MoE) is responsible for implementing the NIPUN Bharat Mission both at the national level and across various States and Union Territories.

Literacy and Numeracy: Literacy refers to the ability to read, write, understand and communicate effectively using written language. It encompasses not only the basic skills of reading but also comprehension, critical thinking and interpretation of written texts. Numeracy on other hand refers to the ability to understand, use, interpret and communicate mathematical information and concepts. It involves being comfortable with numbers, basic calculations, problem solving using mathematical skills and its application in their real life.

Status of Literacy and Numeracy:

The global education landscape was already grappling with a significant learning crisis during the foundational years of children's education. The situation exacerbated with the onset of the pandemic. The closure of schools during lockdowns prevented children from engaging in classroom learning, a critical element for their early-stage growth and development. In India, the impact was profound, with 92% of students experiencing a decline in specific language skills and 82% experiencing a decline in specific math skills compared to the previous year (UNICEF, 2022).

A World Bank assessment highlights that approximately 50% of children in India lack essential foundational learning, leading to difficulties in comprehending and learning at grade level by the time they reach grade 5.

The National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), New Delhi under the MoE guidance, conducted the National Achievement Survey (NAS)-2021 on November 13, 2021, across various schools. The survey assessed students in Classes 3, 5, 8, and 10 in government, government-aided, private recognized, and central government schools. Among the 31 states and union territories that participated in two cycles, 19 showed a decline in language and math outcomes in government schools. Over the past few years, there have been extended periods of school closures, interrupted by short periods of reopening. According to NAS (National Achievement Survey) 2021, the performance percentage in Language is 59, 58 and 62 and in Mathematics 54, 54 and 57 in District (Varanasi), State (Uttar Pradesh) and National wise respectively.

Above disruption was reflected in ASER (Annual Status of Education Report) data collection conducted in Sept-Oct 2022. Interestingly, regions that had lower reading levels in 2018 experienced relatively less learning loss and, in some cases, even witnessed improvements that brought them closer to 2018 levels. For instance, states like Jharkhand, Uttar Pradesh, and Bihar showcased gains surpassing 2018 levels. On the other hand, states like Himachal Pradesh, Kerala, and Punjab, which had

higher reading levels in 2018, experienced more significant learning losses between 2018 and 2022.

Mission PRERNA and NIPUN Bharat Mission:

Mission PRERNA (Program for Result Enhancement Resource Nurturing and Assessment) is a flagship initiative introduced by the Government of Uttar Pradesh, launched in 2020, under the Department of Basic Education across the state. The program is designed to enhance the quality of education across 1.6 lakh govt. schools. It places a special emphasis on improving foundational learning skills for students in grades 1 to 5. These skills encompass crucial abilities such as reading comprehension and basic mathematical calculations, forming the fundamental basis for their future educational pursuits. The primary goal of Mission PRERNA is to ensure that all students from grades 1 to 5 achieve foundational learning by March 2022, thereby significantly enhancing overall learning outcomes in the state. This objective is recognized as a critical necessity. The program encompasses various interventions that collectively aim to ensure that a minimum of 80% of students in each school and block attain foundational learning skills. Successful attainment of these skills will result in designations such as Prerak Student, Prerak School, Prerak Blocks, Prerak Districts, and Prerak Mandals, ultimately culminating in the designation of a Prerak Pradesh.

Subsequently, with the introduction of the NIPUN Bharat mission by the Gol, the Mission PRERNA initiative in Uttar Pradesh has been integrated into the larger framework of the NIPUN Mission. The overarching goals of the NIPUN Bharat Mission include ensuring that children achieve a minimum level of learning, ranging from pre-primary (Balvalitka) to grade 3, specifically in literacy and numeracy skills. These minimum learning standards are referred to as NIPUN lakshya in both language and mathematics within the context of the NIPUN Bharat Mission.

Key Components of the NIPUN Bharat Mission:

- Development of foundational skills to reduce dropout rates and improve the transition to higher classes.
- Enhance education quality through activity-based learning and innovative pedagogies.
- Empowerment of teachers through intensive capacity-building efforts.
- Holistic child development, covering physical and motor skills, socio-emotional growth, literacy and numeracy development, cognitive advancement, and life skills.
- Facilitating steeper learning trajectories for children, which can positively impact their future outcomes and employability.
- Ensuring equitable and inclusive access to quality education for all.

The Government of Uttar Pradesh has aligned the NIPUN lakshya with the state's unique requirements and conditions, adapting it to suit the educational landscape of the region as following-

Language (Hindi):

Grade-1 Read simple sentences consisting 5 words

Grade-2 Read paragraph with 45 words per minute fluency. Answer 75% question correctly after reading.

Grade-3 Read paragraph with 60 words per minute fluency. Answer 75% question correctly after reading

Mathematics:

Grade-1 Solves 75% problems of one digit addition and subtraction correctly

Grade-2 Correctly solved 75% problems of addition (up to 99) and subtraction (two digits)

Grade-3 Correctly solves 75% of the problems of addition (sum up to 999) and subtraction (three digits). Solves 75% of the multiplication problems from 2 to 10 (multiplication up to 100) correctly.

Objectives of the Study: Objectives of the study are as under-

Objective-1- To find out the literacy and numeracy skills among the students enrolled in govt. primary school of Varanasi district.

Objective-2- To find out the literacy and numeracy skills among the students enrolled in govt. primary school of different blocks of Varanasi district.

Objective-3- To find out the correlation between attendance and literacy-numeracy skills among the students enrolled in govt. primary school of Varanasi district.

Methodology: The methodology follows for the present study-

Population- The study focuses on children attending government primary schools in Varanasi. Varanasi has a total of 1009 government primary schools, including both Primary Schools (Grade 1-5) and Composite Schools (Grade 1-8), spread across 08 rural blocks (Arajilines, Baragaon, Chiraigaon, Cholapur, Harahua, Kashividyapith, Pindra, Sewapuri) and 01 urban area (Nagar Kshetra). Within this educational landscape, there are 6601 teachers striving to achieve the NIPUN lakshya among 103738 students out of them 1709 students with disabilities are enrolled in grades 1 to 3 during the academic session-2022-23.

Sample- The study's sample comprises 1006 schools and students enrolled in Grades 1, 2, and 3, totaling 36552, 32522, and 34880 students respectively, thus covering a total of 103454 students out of them 1704 students with disabilities. This sample was assessed through a baseline survey in July 2022. During the end line assessment in March 2023, the study included 861 schools and students in the same grade levels- specifically 28698, 24959, and 26610 students, amounting to a total of 80437 students.

Treatment- The process of achieving the NIPUN lakshya involves the implementation of various strategies by educators and administrative personnel at different levels, including Teachers, Head Teachers, Cluster Officers, Academic Resource Persons (ARPs), Block Education Officers (BEOs), and District Education Officers. These strategies are outlined in a 22-week program provided by the state government, which is guided by teacher manuals. Additionally, regular monthly visits by ARPs help monitor and adjust these strategies to ensure alignment with the NIPUN lakshya goals for Grades 1 to 3.

Data collection- Data collection for the study involves assessing the literacy and numeracy levels of students in Grades 1 to 3. This assessment is carried out through

teacher self-assessment based on the NIPUN lakshya criteria. The study conducted a pre-test or baseline assessment in July 2022 and a post-test or end line assessment in March 2023. Data was collected using Google Forms, primarily relying on teacher self-assessment. This process identified students as NIPUN or not in Language (Hindi) and Mathematics during both the baseline and end line assessments. The study involved 1006 schools in the baseline assessment and 861 schools in the end line assessment.

Analysis and Result- The collected data, measured on a nominal scale, was analyzed using percentage-based methods. The frequency of NIPUN students in Language (Hindi), Mathematics, and both subjects was analyzed through teacher self-assessment. Teachers determined whether students met the NIPUN lakshya criteria for Language (Hindi) or Mathematics or both, based on the grade-specific NIPUN lakshya standards

Table-1 NIPUN student in Language (Hindi)

	Grade-1		Grade-2		Grade-3		Grade-1-3	
	Total students	Nipun students						
July-22	36552	15249	32522	16923	34880	17433	103954	49605
March-23	28698	19448	24959	17354	26610	18967	80437	56235

The data presented in Table-1 and the accompanying graph demonstrates the progress of Grade-1, 2, and 3 students under the NIPUN assessment in Language (Hindi). In July 2022, their proficiency percentages were 41.72%, 52.04%, and 49.98%, respectively. However, in March 2023, these percentages significantly increased to 67.77%, 69.53%, and 71.28%, indicating substantial improvement. Notably, in March 2023, their overall performance of 69.48% surpassed the 47.72% recorded in July 2022, particularly in Language (Hindi). Result reveals that after completion of 22 week FLN programme there are 67.77%(+26.05) students able to read simple sentences consisting 5 words in grade-1, 69.53%(+17.49) students able to read paragraph with 45 words per minute fluency and answer 75% question correctly after reading in grade-2, and 71.28%(+21.30) students able to read paragraph with minimum 60 words per

minute fluency and answer 75% question correctly after reading in grade-3. These outcomes highlight the effectiveness of the FLN program in enhancing literacy skills among the targeted students. Thus above analysis and results fulfill the objective no.1 particular in Literacy skills.

Table-2 NIPUN student in Mathematics

	Grade-1		Grade-2		Grade-3		Grade-1-3	
	Total students	Nipun students						
July-22	36552	14476	32522	16904	34880	17613	103954	48993
March-23	28698	20111	24959	17795	26610	19359	80437	57718

Table-2 and the accompanying graph illustrate the NIPUN assessment results for Grade-1, 2, and 3 students in Mathematics. In July 2022, their proficiency percentages were 36.60%, 51.98%, and 50.50% respectively. However, in March 2023, these percentages substantially improved to 70.08%, 71.30%, and 72.25% respectively. Notably, there was a significant rise from 47.13% in July 2022 to 71.34% in March 2023, demonstrating remarkable progress in Mathematics. It reveals that after completion of 22 week FLN programme there are 70.08%(+30.47) students able to solves 75% problems of one digit addition and subtraction correctly in grade-1, 71.30%(+19.32) students can correctly solved 75% problems of addition (up to 99) and subtraction (two digits) in grade-2 and 72.75%(+22.25) students able to correctly solves 75% of the problems of addition (sum up to 999) and subtraction (three digits) and solves 75% of the multiplication problems from 2 to 10 (multiplication up to 100) correctly in grade-3. These findings underscore the effectiveness of the FLN program in enhancing numeracy skills among the children. It is clear that analysis and results fulfill the objective no.1 particular in Numeracy skills.

Table-3 NIPUN student in Language (Hindi) and Mathematics

	Grade-1		Grade-2		Grade-3		Grade-1-3	
	Total students	Nipun students						
July-22	36552	13077	32522	15354	34880	16021	103954	44452
March-23	28698	19313	24959	17175	26610	18707	80437	55195

Table-3 and the corresponding graph present the NIPUN assessment outcomes for students in Grades 1, 2, and 3. In July 2022, their proficiency percentages stood at 35.78%, 47.21%, and 45.93% respectively. However, by March 2023, these figures notably increased to 67.30%, 68.81%, and 70.30% respectively. Significantly, there was a substantial improvement from 42.76% in July 2022 to 68.76% in March 2023, demonstrating marked advancements in both Language (Hindi) and Mathematics.

The result reveals that after completion of 22 week FLN programme 67.30%(+31.52) students able to read simple sentences consisting 5 words and solves 75% maths problems of one digit addition and subtraction correctly in grade-1. In other hand 68.81%(+21.60) students able to read paragraph with 45 words per minute fluency answer 75% question correctly after reading and correctly solved 75% maths problems of addition (up to 99) and subtraction (two digits) in grade-2. In the same fashion 70.30%(+24.37) students able to read paragraph with 60 words per minute fluency and answer 75% question correctly after reading and correctly solves 75% of the problems of addition (sum up to 999) and subtraction (three digits) and solves 75% of the multiplication problems from 2 to 10 (multiplication up to 100) correctly in grade-3.

This underscores the efficacy of the FLN program in enhancing foundational literacy and numeracy skills within the targeted student group which fulfill the objective no.1 completely.

Table-4 Block wise NIPUN student in Language (Hindi) and Mathematics

SN	Block	July 22		March 23	
		Total students	Nipun students	Total students	Nipun students
1	Arajilines	16254	9591	12470	9210
2	Baragaon	10646	5398	5296	3680
3	Chiraigaon	12621	4850	7288	3862
4	Cholapur	10914	4469	8170	5749
5	Harahua	10740	2916	9858	6939
6	Kashividyapith	10710	4196	8488	5886
7	Pindra	12047	4308	10861	6379
8	Sewapuri	11951	5067	10641	9032
9	Nagar Kshetra	8071	3657	7365	4458
	Total	103954	44452	80437	55195

The data presented in Table-4 and the accompanying graph highlight the performance and of students in Language (Hindi) and Mathematics for the periods of July 2022 and March 2023 area wise. The table indicates that out of a total of 103,954 students, 44,452 students achieved the NIPUN status in both Language (Hindi) and Mathematics in July 2022. While in March 2023, a total of 80,437 students were assessed and 55,195 of them were deemed NIPUN in both subjects. This suggests a positive trend in student proficiency over this period. On the other hand Harahua block, there was a notable improvement of 43.24% in the group performance of Language (Hindi) and Mathematics from July 2022 to March 2023. This improvement shows the dedication and efforts of students, teachers and the educational system in enhancing academic outcomes and analysis & results completely fulfill the objective no.2.

Table-5 Relation between NIPUN student and Attendance (March-2023)

SN	Block	NIPUN %	Attendance %
1	Arajilines	73.86	72.71
2	Baragaon	69.70	77.72
3	Chiraigaon	52.99	69.62
4	Cholapur	70.42	72.67

5	Harahua	70.39	71.57
6	Kashividyapith	69.76	71.81
7	Pindra	59.09	72.38
8	Sewapuri	84.88	76.37
9	Nagar Kshetra	60.79	68.83
	Total	68.76	72.63

Correlation

		NIPUN Student (%)	Attendance (%)
NIPUN Student (%)	Pearson Correlation	1	.673 [*]
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	.047
	N	9	9
Attendance (%)	Pearson Correlation	.673 [*]	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.047	-
	N	9	9

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The findings from an assessment conducted in March 2023, focusing on the correlation between the percentage of students categorized as NIPUN and their average attendance. NIPUN students are likely those who demonstrate NIPUN lakshya. According to the data, 68.76% of students were identified as NIPUN, and the average attendance rate was 72.63% during the same period.

The correlation analysis consists of a matrix that displays Pearson correlation coefficients between NIPUN student percentage and attendance percentage. The coefficients are calculated for both factors individually, resulting in a correlation value of

0.673 between NIPUN percentage and attendance percentage. This value signifies a moderately strong positive correlation.

The 'Sig. (2-tailed)' value of 0.047 indicates the p-value associated with the correlation coefficient. A p-value below a certain threshold (often 0.05) is considered statistically significant. In this case the p-value is less than 0.05, which further supports the idea that the observed correlation is unlikely to have occurred by chance. Hence the above analysis and results fulfill the objective no.3 completely.

Discussion:

The data presented in the provided tables and graphs illustrate the impact of the FLN program on student's proficiency in both Language (Hindi) and Mathematics across different grade levels. The assessment was conducted in July 2022 and March 2023, allowing for a comparison of student's performance before and after the 22 week FLN programme implementation. The results indicate consistent and notable improvements in student's proficiency rates across various categories:

Literacy: The data in Table-1 demonstrate that students in Grade-1, 2 and 3 exhibited substantial increases in Language (Hindi) proficiency percentage between July 2022 and March 2023. Grade 3 students shows the highest 71.28% proficiency in Language (Hindi) and grade 1 students shows the highest increase with proficiency percentage with 67.77%(+26.05) in Language (Hindi). It reveal substantial improvement compare to NAS-2021 report where grade-3 student's performance in Language were 59 in Varanasi also ASER-2022 reported only 23.9% were able to read grade-2 level text in Uttar Pradesh.

Numeracy: Table-2 show significant improvement in Mathematics proficiency after the implementation of the FLN programme. Grade-1 students demonstrated remarkable growth in Mathematics proficiency in numeracy skills. Grade 3 students shows the highest 72.75% proficiency in Mathematics and grade 1 students shows the highest increase with proficiency percentage with 70.08%(+30.47) in Language (Hindi). It shows remarkable improvement compare to NAS-2021 report where grade-3 student's performance in Mathematics was 54 in Varanasi.

NIPUN students: Table-3 reveals that the combined proficiency in both Language (Hindi) and Mathematics improves equally on all grade levels, indicating a holistic impact of the FLN program on foundational skills development. Grade 3 students shows the highest 70.30% proficiency in FLN and grade 1 students shows the highest increase with proficiency percentage with 67.30%(+31.52) in Language (Hindi) and Mathematics. Additionally, Table-4 highlights an increase in the number of NIPUN students in Language (Hindi) and Mathematics from July 2022 to March 2023, indicating that a larger proportion of students benefited from the program over time in which Harahua block improved of (+)43.24% more than the targeted goal.

Attendance: A positive correlation (+0.673) was found between NIPUN student percentage and average attendance, indicating a relationship between attendance and literacy/numeracy skills. Thus higher attendance percentage is associated with higher percentage of NIPUN students of literacy and numeracy skills.

Conclusion:

The evidence presented in the tables and graphs indicates that the FLN (Foundational Literacy and Numeracy) programme of 22 week has been successful in improving literacy and numeracy skills among students with and without disabilities. The impact of programme is evident in various aspects-

Substantial Improvement: The significant increases in proficiency percentages between the two assessment periods clearly demonstrate that the FLN program has effectively enhanced student's foundational skills.

Consistency across Grades: The program's positive impact is observed consistently across Grade-1, 2, and 3 students, underscoring its universal applicability.

Holistic Development: The FLN program's effectiveness extends to both Language (Hindi) and Mathematics, indicating its role in promoting well-rounded foundational skills.

Attendance and Proficiency Relationship: The correlation between attendance and proficiency, as shown in Table-5, reinforces the importance of regular attendance in achieving better literacy and numeracy outcomes. Finally, the FLN programme of 22 week is equally improving foundational Literacy and numeracy skills among students with and without disabilities. NIPUN Bharat mission in Varanasi not only fulfils the objectives of NEP-2020 but also fulfils the dream of Govt. of Uttar Pradesh and Govt. of India.

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